

When Nature Becomes the Base in *Riders to the Sea*: Eco-Critical Reflections on Myth and Mortality

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Abstract

J.M. Synge's *Riders to the Sea* is a one act tragedy, set in the Aran Islands, located on the western coast of Ireland. He depicted this particular geographical area, where a traditional life-style prevails and also the community's struggle for existence against the nature. This paper tries to explore 'Sea' as a force of nature over which nobody of the island has any control. Opposing the sea and opposed by the sea, are the members of the community living on the island. The nature-man conflict dominates the whole play. The symbolic meaning of the sea has been enriched through the intersections of Irish myth and folklore. The very aspect of ecological reality along with the spiritual and mythical understanding of mortality rooted in natural cycles has been delineated through eco-critical analysis that tries to address the universal character of human suffering and loss and that is in harmony with nature. This paper attempts to foster a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness between humans and natural world.

Keywords: Struggle, Conflict, Myth, Folklore, Mortality, Eco-critical analysis

Introduction

Eco-criticism is a critical approach to literature and culture that focuses on the relationship between human beings and the natural world. It emerged in the 1990s as a response to growing concerns about environmental degradation and the impact of human activity on the planet. (Glotfelty and Fromm)

It is a theoretical framework of this interdisciplinary approach that explores the symbiotic relationship between any literary work and the natural environment. This approach is deeply rooted in the understanding that apart from depicting nature, this literary work also provides an insight into the interconnectedness of the universal character of human suffering, death and mortality. *Riders to the Sea* (1904) is set on the Aran Islands, off the west coast of

Ireland—a remote, harsh and sea-bound region. It is the hard reality that islanders have to completely rely on the mercy of the waves. The sea as a natural force has been projected both as the source of life and the destroyer of life. The islanders solely depend on sea as far as their survival is concerned. Apart from fishing they collect sea weeds as a source of fuel. Similarly, myth and mortality coincide within the framework of eco-critical reflection.

Objectives of the Study

- To explore how this present literary work has grappled with human vulnerability in the face of nature's power
- To provide cultural framework for understanding ecological realities
- To empathise the traditional communities who are otherwise devoured by the cruel sea
- To examine the interplay of nature, myth and mortality

Literature Review

The term eco-criticism was formalized in the 1990s by Cheryll Glotfelty and Harold Fromm in *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology* (1996). Eco-criticism emphasizes that nature is not merely a passive backdrop in literature, but an active agent influencing characters, themes and ideology. It draws on interdisciplinary approaches to analyse the representation of nature in literature.

The main aspect to ecocriticism is the recognition of nature that appears to be a dynamic force in the process of shaping culture and identity. The ways the notion of landscape, animals, plants and ecosystems are depicted in the literary texts are reflected in eco-critical framework. (Garrard, 2004; Nixon, 2011)

Synge employed myth, folklore and ritual of Irish peasant life especially the inhabitants of the Aran Islands. Maurya, an old woman, is the matriarch of her family. She becomes an archetype of maternal suffering and loss. She describes the destruction of men of the family. It shows that the struggle of all the riders to the sea with the elements and the cycle of death in the backdrop of the ancient ritual of the community and finally the stoic resignation and dignity of the old woman. Maury's declaration towards the end of the play "The're all gone now, and there isn't anything more the sea can do to me" is an expression of surrender to the overwhelming power of the environment. (Kiberd, 1995; Garrard, 2004)

The play *Riders to the Sea* portrays local ecological vulnerability. The struggle that the inhabitants of the Aran Islands undergoes reflects the struggle, suffering and loss of other indigenous communities around the world. (Heise, 2008)

The Gaelic speech patterns spoken in rural areas, Catholic belief systems, and oral storytelling traditions of the islanders accentuate his profound commitment to Irish folklore. Local legends and spiritual beliefs were documented, when Synge went to the Aran Islands in

1898. The whole play reflects the spiritual ecology of the Aran islanders, where the sea is a constant threat to the fishermen's lives.

Methodology

The present paper employs a qualitative approach in order to assess the eco-critical reflection in *Riders to the Sea* within the framework of nature, myth and mortality. The research design comprises of the review of related literature and analysis of articles, books and other relevant sources on the related field. It is analytical in the sense that the paper attempts to ascertain the dimensions of eco-critical perspectives and interpretations present in the literary text under discussion. The methodology has been adopted in order to ensure an ample understanding of the eco critical ramifications of *Riders to the Sea* through close reading and textual analysis. The primary text serves as the main source of data. Relevant secondary sources such as articles, books focusing on the intersection of natural ecology and literature are taken into account. These resources provide a necessary base to interpret and validate the ecological consciousness rooted in the text.

The analysis underscores the cultural and geographical background of the Aran Islands and paves the way for ecological setting taking into consideration of various thematic elements, mythical undertones, rituals, prayers, folk customs, imagery, supernatural elements, and symbolism.

Since the present paper solely focuses on analyzing a literary text and its associated scholarly literature, confidentiality and privacy of individuals are not relevant in this regard. It has been tried to acknowledge the citations and referencing of all sources used in the present paper.

Discussion

The scene of action is laid in a cottage kitchen off the West of Ireland and the author addresses the tragic happenings of a family residing there, who, try to carry on their lives among the relentless sea. The sea as a symbol stands as a connector to the outside world. It provides sustenance no doubt, but at the same time, it also takes life. As a result the family has to pay a very heavy price at the end. It is the tragedy of everymen, pitted against the violent force of a cold, relentless natural element, that is, the sea. The grim reality is accentuated when we are informed that Maurya had already lost six loved ones to the ocean comprising of her father-in-law, her husband and four of her sons. In this sense they are all riders to the sea who are devoured by the destructive force of nature. Here destiny or fate plays a very important role.

Death is predetermined for her then two surviving sons: Michael and Bartley. It becomes a kind of universal human suffering and death. Maurya's remark with calm resignation towards the end of the play justifies her acceptance when she says "They're all gone now, and

there isn't anything more the sea can do to me..." The tone is stoical here when she understands the power of fate.

The sea has become an 'archetype' of the uncertainty of human life at the cost of nature's destructive power. The sea has appeared as a boon and curse at the same time. The spiritual and mythical ramifications have been evident throughout the play. The Gaelic tradition, the keening practice, the reference of black hags, spirits haunting the seas, dreams nestled with premonitions and the cycles of death etc. are all mythical motifs. Maurya's engaging with wailing echoes the kind of indigenous belief system of Ireland. Maurya sees the ghost of her dead son 'Michael' and interprets this as a sign that the last son Bartley is doomed. She says: "... and I stood there saying a prayer to myself. Then Bartley came along, and he riding on the red mare with the gray pony behind him". Here the colour motif implies that 'red' stands for life full of blood signifying vitality and 'gray' representing melancholic overtones. There are various references to religious influence throughout the play. The vision that Maurya sees has some kind of prophesy of her last son's impending death. It's a part of mythical vision. She sees that Michael wears fine clothes and new shoes on his feet. Similarly, this scene possesses a kind of mystic element when Maurya cites the popular Irish folklore of Bride Dara, when she says "...since the day Bride Dara seen the dead man with the child in his arms." The reference of Holy Water that Maurya asked Nora is also a part and parcel of traditional Catholic death rituals practised by Aran islanders. Holy water is sprinkled over the dead is an ultimate acceptance by kneeling down before fate and mortality.

The theme of Mortality resonates with the idea of redemption through spiritual inclination. The repeated experience of death and mortality is apparent when Maurya mentions the reference of her deceased sons: Shawn, Sheamus, Stephen, Patch; her husband and father-in-law. Maurya's grieving for Michael for nine days is now coupled with the fear of losing Bartley, her only remaining son. Mortality has become a part of ecological cycle. Towards the end of the play, it transcends the level of mere surrendering to the universal truth, ultimately attaining the zenith of human resilience, when Murya concludes: "No man at all can be living for ever, and we must be satisfied."

Conclusion

From the foregoing discussion and analysis, it can be inferred that *Riders to the Sea* has a sharp ecological framework that embraces a kind of interplay of nature, myth and mortality. The play is a perfect example of the characteristics of Synge's dramatic pattern in order to preserve and celebrate Irish identity through theatre. It becomes a popular narrative in presenting the conflict between the raging sea and the humble humanity. The nature is presented in binary terms, that is, nature as life-giving to the inhabitants in the form of livelihood and nature as life-taking in the form of causing death repeatedly to the near and dear ones of the protagonist. Here in this case, sea has been projected in duality. All the male characters in the play are the riders to the sea for their survival, but the irony is that the sea never spares them. We, the humans, are nobody, just a puppet in the hands of fate. The nature has become a metaphor for God's will.

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